

Quantum state tomography as a numerical optimization problem – Supplemental Material

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We parametrize states which are effectively in a four dimensional Hilbert space, $|\psi\rangle = \sum_{i=1}^4 x_i|i\rangle$, by six real parameters, $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3$ and $\varphi_2, \varphi_3, \varphi_4$, as follows,

$$x_1 = \cos \theta_1, \tag{1}$$

$$x_2 = \sin \theta_1 \cos \theta_2 e^{i\varphi_2}, \tag{2}$$

$$x_3 = \sin \theta_1 \sin \theta_2 \cos \theta_3 e^{i\varphi_3}, \tag{3}$$

$$x_4 = \sin \theta_1 \sin \theta_2 \sin \theta_3 e^{i\varphi_4}. \tag{4}$$

Here we give the parameters for the vectors forming the rank-3 projectors $P_2, \dots, P_{35}$ of our numerically optimized quorum for QST in a qubit-qutrit system by measuring the qubit. The projector P_1 projects on the qubit state $|0\rangle$. The parametrization is according to Eqs. (1)-(4) (lower index). We have three vectors per projector indicated by the second upper index, the first upper index denotes the number of the projector

$$\begin{aligned} & (\theta_1^{2,1}, \theta_1^{3,1}, \dots, \theta_1^{35,1}, \theta_2^{2,1}, \theta_2^{3,1}, \dots, \theta_2^{35,1}, \theta_3^{2,1}, \theta_3^{3,1}, \dots, \theta_3^{35,1}, \varphi_2^{2,1}, \varphi_2^{3,1}, \dots, \varphi_2^{35,1}, \varphi_3^{2,1}, \varphi_3^{3,1}, \dots, \varphi_3^{35,1}, \varphi_4^{2,1}, \varphi_4^{3,1}, \dots, \varphi_4^{35,1}, \\ & \theta_1^{2,2}, \theta_1^{3,2}, \dots, \theta_1^{35,2}, \theta_2^{2,2}, \theta_2^{3,2}, \dots, \theta_2^{35,2}, \theta_3^{2,2}, \theta_3^{3,2}, \dots, \theta_3^{35,2}, \varphi_2^{2,2}, \varphi_2^{3,2}, \dots, \varphi_2^{35,2}, \varphi_3^{2,2}, \varphi_3^{3,2}, \dots, \varphi_3^{35,2}, \varphi_4^{2,2}, \varphi_4^{3,2}, \dots, \varphi_4^{35,2}, \\ & \theta_1^{2,3}, \theta_1^{3,3}, \dots, \theta_1^{35,3}, \theta_2^{2,3}, \theta_2^{3,3}, \dots, \theta_2^{35,3}, \theta_3^{2,3}, \theta_3^{3,3}, \dots, \theta_3^{35,3}, \varphi_2^{2,3}, \varphi_2^{3,3}, \dots, \varphi_2^{35,3}, \varphi_3^{2,3}, \varphi_3^{3,3}, \dots, \varphi_3^{35,3}, \varphi_4^{2,3}, \varphi_4^{3,3}, \dots, \varphi_4^{35,3}) \\ = & (2.257693865798901, 1.20946376090225, 0.9509877560122885, 1.099178941400538, -0.879453414994822, \\ & 2.648162761676451, 0.9509546789661947, 2.376381592479905, -0.5593584876675007, 0.97222586587755, \\ & 1.005902832943661, 1.424139438093924, 2.51739653038681, 1.912998755250953, 0.9537196675796634, \\ & -0.9371691961451061, 1.135467407115008, 2.18572724020349, 1.378244433590597, 2.177304513636702, \\ & 2.42269551849275, 1.480024727657586, 1.247107128233221, 3.91582765645886, 1.13360414637495, \\ & 1.890994544340926, 1.927110371230943, 1.101037103665153, 1.896469082366562, 1.27312342613534, \\ & 0.866254425515995, 1.405456110688733, 1.830156934667931, 5.472509003440993, 1.357827494469045, \\ & 1.528400959120926, 0.776144056523342, 1.766506537596669, 1.087036749589844, 0.5741681752593587, \\ & 2.01525358280448, 0.874555091721569, 1.033745474865665, 2.306611746205063, 0.8843770804517408, \\ & 0.6922460476820547, 0.5550878847124262, 0.869536066640765, 0.8989797138590121, 1.135753699369441, \\ & -0.6686711784063227, 2.241445738859443, -1.414126718979912, 1.149584169860139, 1.131160391779805, \\ & -0.9406036882895227, 1.367858618798337, 1.097575821848382, 1.19381919939491, 0.864109413151236, \\ & 0.9135466939475426, -4.236917134584685, 2.206880467566779, 0.8595654852753031, -1.40675409564935, \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

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The choice of unitary operations, which are needed to transform the 4D subspace to the appropriate subspace in our actual 6D space is not unique. We choose them in the following way: The first (or the first and second) column of 6×6 matrix is the first vector (or the first and the second vectors) selected and then we add 5 (4) out of the 6 standard basis vectors, where we exclude the vector (or two basis vectors) which are the most similar to the selected vector (vectors). In the first case we have one selected vector and want to transform the second vector and in the second case, discussed above, we aim to transform the 3rd vector. After we select these vectors, we apply the Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization method to obtain an orthonormal vector set.